

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
**EDUCATION AND
TECHNOLOGY (AJET)**

ISSN: 2832-9481 (ONLINE)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 2 (2022)

Indexed in

PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

Teachers' Self-Efficacy and Their Performance Appraisal in Public Secondary Schools

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Article Information

Received: August 30, 2022

Accepted: September 21, 2022

Published: September 24, 2022

Keywords

Performance Appraisal, Self-Efficacy, Secondary Schools, Kenya

ABSTRACT

This paper aimed to assess the effect of teachers' self-efficacy on their performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Sabatia Sub County, Vihiga County, Kenya. The study, anchored on the social cognitive theory, adopted correlational and descriptive survey research designs. Stratified random sampling was used to select 12 schools and 227 teachers for the study based on category of school, status, and gender. Principals of each sampled school and the Sabatia Sub-County Teachers' Service Commission director were purposively sampled. Data for the study was collected using questionnaires, interview guide, and document analysis guide. Quality assurance of research instruments ensured through piloting, content validity and test retest for reliability. Quantitative data was analysed using SPSS (version 25.0) descriptively and inferentially, while qualitative data was analyzed thematically. The findings showed the R-value from the model summary of the regression between self-efficacy and performance appraisal was 0.617. The R square value was 0.381, which implied 38.1 % effect on self-efficacy was attributed to teacher appraisal. The findings show significant effect of self-efficacy on performance appraisal. Therefore, performance appraisal for teachers needs to be enhanced since it plays a significant role in boosting their confidence, thus their self-efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

Self-efficacy is the belief in one's capabilities to achieve a goal or an outcome. In a teaching context self-efficacy refers to the ability to determine the outcomes of the students work (Shahzad & Naureen, 2017). According to Lewis (2007), self-efficacy is a self-evaluation of whether a person feels they can accomplish a certain task or not. Efficacy beliefs have been shown to affect teacher activity and productivity. Teacher efficacy has been associated with teachers' choice of instructional decisions in content delivery, confidence in task performance, and learner outcomes. Teaching is a profession in which it is truly a boon to have a strong sense of self-efficacy. A teacher needs to deal with young, energetic, and or hormonal students all day. Teachers combine their relevant skills, experiences and positive attitudes towards the profession, in order to raise the quality of the schools' academic performance. This combination is achieved through instructional appraisal, an aspect which has motivated the researcher to initiate this study.

Performance appraisal is a process designed to evaluate, manage and ultimately improve teacher's performance. It should allow the employer and teacher to openly discuss the expectations of the institution and the achievements of the teacher (OECD, 2013). In Kenya, teachers' performance appraisal was birthed because of challenges experienced in education system since independence. This was in bid to improve the quality of education. In 1964, Ominde Commission proposed policy recommendations touching on aspects of education like a suggestion that required teachers be evaluated through inspections. This informed the government of Kenya's initiation of inspectorial evaluation of schools and teaching to improve

standards of education (Ominde, 1964).

Chapter 211, section 18 of the 1980 Education Act entrusted the Ministry of Education through the inspectorate, which changed to Directorate of Quality Assurance and Standards in 2003, with provision of quality education. The act mandated the minister to appoint inspectors to inspect any school any time with or without notice and report on the state of the school (Republic of Kenya, 2012). This was to establish if the curriculum was properly implemented and whether teachers were competent professionals.

Publication of a revised code of teachers was done in 2005 changing the appraisal policy from confidential to an open appraisal system (OPAS) (TSC, 2005). Heads of institutions were therefore required to play an overall role in the performance appraisal for teachers in their respective institutions (TSC, 2014). To improve on OPAS and its outcome, the commission introduced Teachers Performance Appraisal and Development (TPAD) in 2014 (TSC/TPAD/01). The TSC/TPAD/01 indicated that the purpose of ongoing appraisal was to review and improve teaching standards through a systematic appraisal approach with a view to evaluate teachers' performance and promote professional development so as to enhance learning outcomes. Its objectives were: to provide quality education to learners in all public institutions, to provide an opportunity for teachers to improve their performance competencies, to analyze performance gaps, to provide support for professional development, and to provide a fair, effective and consistent teacher evaluation (TSC/TPAD/01).

In administering the performance appraisal, the Code of Regulations (2015) for teachers stipulated that:

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Heads of institutions were to provide oversight role in the performance appraisal for the teachers in their respective institutions, use performance appraisal reports for purposes of promotion, deployment, and other rewards as may be prescribed from time to time, identify training needs and taking correction measures in cases of unsatisfactory performance among others.

According to appraisal tool, failure to comply with appraisal requirements may attract disciplinary action against a teacher who: Fails to complete and submit an appraisal report to the supervisor, or refuses or neglects to discuss or sign the appraisal report with the supervisor, consistently displays poor performance or adverse appraisal ratings may after due process have his services terminated. Performance appraisal of teachers is very critical in that it helps in identification of an individual's current level of job performance, motivation and helps them in identifying training and development needs, provides information for succession planning, enables coaching and counseling of teachers and principals, improves internal communication and thus helps in setting performance goals and assessing potential for promotion of teachers among many others. Despite the significance of teacher appraisal, critiques argue that it does not necessarily affect the quality of teaching which ultimately manifest in terms of improved educational standards because of its blindness to other vital teacher aspects like efficacy. This was clearly depicted in the Kenya Secondary Schools Heads Association Vihiga County Academic meeting held in Nakuru on 25th – 28th February 2018. In this meeting it was reported that only 1510 out of 13053 students who sat Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) in 2017 attained grade C+ and above.

Researchers have engaged in studies on aspects of teachers' self-efficacy and teachers' appraisal and given their recommendations. For instance, Agesa (2005) worked on the effects of employee appraisal on performance of teachers. He argues that the appraisal systems should not be used by Principals to discriminate against teachers on basis of age, gender, ethnicity, or political affiliations among others. Oginga, Muola, and

Mwania (2014) in a study found out that teachers' self-efficacies in special needs and HIV/AIDS education were low and that the low teachers' efficacy negatively affected curriculum implementation by teachers.

In Sabatia Sub- County, the major aim of appraisal is to develop teachers in order to improve their service delivery in schools. Instructional appraisal aids Principals in coordinating, improving and maintaining high teaching and learning standards in schools (Maranya, 2001). Kadenyi (2014) in a study on 'Influence of teacher appraisal on improvement of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Vihiga Sub-county, Kenya found a significant relationship between teachers' appraisal and students' academic performance. A study by Odanga, Raburu, and Aloka (2018) on 'Strategies for enhancing Teachers' self-efficacy' revealed that topics covered in seminars and workshops for secondary school teachers in Kisumu County between 2011 and 2015, included; child protection, school dropout and exam rating, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) integration and performance appraisal. This shows that the seminars and workshops did not address low teachers' self-efficacy. Studies elsewhere have demonstrated that self-efficacy is a natural protective factor against teacher job strain, job stress, and burnout. It was against this background that the study assessed effect of teacher efficacy on performance appraisal.

Objective of the Study

To assess the effect of teachers' self-efficacy on their performance appraisal among public secondary school teachers in Sabatia Sub- County, Vihiga County, Kenya.

Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and teacher's performance appraisal among public secondary school teachers in Sabatia Sub-County, Vihiga County, Kenya.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the interaction between teachers' self-efficacy and performance appraisal

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Author conceptualization (2021)

The conceptual framework shows that teachers' self-efficacy affects their performance appraisal. Teachers with a strong belief in their abilities are more likely to rate highly in performance of their duties. Such teachers

exhibit high levels of professional knowledge, innovation and creativity, and time management. This results from taking time to thoroughly prepare for lessons and positivity to enhance their professional knowledge and skills.

Empirical Literature

The study is anchored on the Social Cognitive theory by Albert Bandura (1967). According to social cognitive theory, effective learning happens when an individual is in a social context and able to engage in both dynamic and reciprocal interactions between the person, the environment, and the behavior (Lamovate, 2016). Social cognitive theory is based on six constructs; Reciprocal determinism: the dynamic interaction of person and behavior, behavioral capability: the individual's actual ability to perform the appropriate behavior, observational learning: learning a new skill or piece of knowledge by observing others (and potentially modeling them as well), reinforcements: the external responses to the individual's behavior that either encourage or discourage the behavior, expectations: the anticipated consequences of behavior, and self-efficacy: the person's confidence in his or her ability to perform a behavior (Lamovate, 2016).

The social cognitive theory considers many separate, unique contextual variables when predicting or explaining a person's behavior, giving it a broad range of potential applications including health, local environment, and the local community. The ultimate goal is to explain how people regulate their behavior through control and reinforcement to achieve goal-directed behavior that can be mastered over time. According to Henson, R.K. (2001), self-efficacy influences our choices, our effort, our persistence when facing adversity, and our emotions.

Teachers are vital for an education system on the ground (Shahzad K. and Naureen S., 2017). Thus, the more competent the teachers are, the more effective is the education system. Teachers' competency is based on self-efficacy. When teachers are competent, they impact students' performance. Lack of self-efficacy causes many psychological problems like low confidence level and low self-esteem.

Ashton and Webb (1998) explain that teachers who have a higher level of self-efficacy are more organized, have a greater skill of instruction and questioning, have better abilities to explain and can solve academic problems easily. On the other hand, teachers with a low level of self-efficacy seem more confused; feel threatened to be questioned, cannot maintain tasks and feel difficulty in countering student affairs. Hence, students' performance is highly associated with teachers' self-efficacy.

Tournaki and Podell (2005) published records of more than three hundred teachers about the influence of their behavior on student success and teacher vision and predictions about students. Their findings revealed that teachers with high efficacy predict most of the time accurately and in case of wrong predictions, they somehow try to understand why they predicted incorrectly; whereas teachers with low efficacy mostly predict wrongly about their students and sometimes even got harsh in difficult situations.

Mojavezi (2012) conducted a study with a similar topic in four different cities of Iran having 80 senior high school teachers and 150 senior high school students. He

administered teacher self-efficacy scale to gauge teacher sense of self-efficacy beliefs and a questionnaire to weigh students' motivational level. He then divided the teachers into groups according to their level of self-efficacy and discussed the impact of teacher's self-efficacy on the students' academic achievement. His findings agreed with Bandura's observation (1994) that teachers with high sense of self-efficacy about their competence can motivate their cognitive development. These results suggest that teacher self-efficacy has a positive impact on students' behavior, learning and achievement.

OECD's Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) which involved 90,000 secondary school teachers and principals across 24 countries found that the greater the emphasis placed on specific aspects of teaching in the feedback offered through the performance appraisal process, the greater the impact teachers believed it had on their teaching (OECD, 2009). This provides useful insight into the formative aspects of appraisal and the extent to which teachers believe the process assists in developing their practice. According to 2009 TALIS report (OECD, 2009) appraisal and feedback have a strong influence on teachers, increasing job satisfaction and improving teaching practice. Performance appraisal needs to provide feedback to teachers about their professional practice and opportunities for improvement. Although Danielson and Donaldson (2012) report that teachers need constructive feedback from a skilled practitioner in order to improve their teaching, research suggests that feedback is often not a common occurrence in schools (OECD, 2009, Zatyński, 2012).

A study by Birman, LeFloch, Klekotka, Ludwig, Taylor, Walters, Wayne and Yoon (2007) on professional development in mathematics shows that few teachers receive intensive, sustained, and content-focused professional development in mathematics. Teachers averaged 8.3 hours of professional development on how to teach mathematics and 5.2 hours on the "in-depth study" of topics in mathematics during the 12 months spanning the 2003/04 school year and the summer of 2004. Of elementary teachers, 71 percent participated in professional development focused on instructional strategies for teaching mathematics. But only 9 percent participated for more than 24 hours during the one-year period. Even fewer elementary school teachers (49 percent) reported that they participated in professional development focused on the in-depth study of mathematics during the same time period, and only 6 percent participated for more than 24 hours. Of secondary mathematics teachers, 51 percent attended professional development focused on the in-depth study of mathematics, but only 10 percent spent more than 24 hours on that content during the year.

Previous studies have found that employees with stronger creative self-efficacy are more likely to engage in higher levels of creativity in their work (Gong, Y. P, Huancy, J. C. and Farh, J. L, 2009). Studies indicate that highly efficacious teachers are more likely to implement

instructional innovation in the classroom (Zhao & Cziko, 2001 cited in Teo, 2009). For instance, Palaniappan (2009) compared creativity levels of Malaysian and American students. He reported that American students are significantly superior to their Malaysian counterparts in general creativity as well as in its components, namely fluency, flexibility, originality and elaboration.

When it comes to teaching innovation, according to Bruce, learning occurs in the interaction between the learner and the learning environment; when the appropriate strategies and skills are applied to technology use, making it a favorable tool for teaching, then better teaching effectiveness can be developed (Bruce, 2009). Wu pointed out that teaching innovation (during the teaching process) is when teachers use multi-faceted and lively teaching methods, and diversified and rich content to stimulate students' inner interest in learning, thus, developing positive student attitudes toward proactive learning and enhancing students' learning ability (Wu, 2002). Lin believed that teaching innovation involves teachers having an open mind, having the ability to reflect on teaching and being able to use the cogitative skills of reflection, questioning, deconstruction and reconstruction to guide students to learn correctly and to develop students' critical thinking and creative capabilities (Lin, 2002).

METHODOLOGY

The sphere of pragmatism involves merging of the positivism and interpretivism paradigms in a single study. Pragmatism, which considers both the objective and the subjective nature of knowledge, is based on the view that the world is real and socially constructed, and that knowledge is socially shared, because it comes from socially shared experiences (Morgan, 2014). The study was guided by pragmatism paradigm to adopt a mixed methods design. Creswell (2007) describes mixed methods research as consisting of a combination of qualitative and quantitative research approaches. According to Creswell & Creswell (2018), employing a mixed methods research design yields more information that provides more in depth understanding of phenomena under study. In this study, correlational and descriptive survey research designs

were adopted. Correlational research design is appropriate as it makes attempt to establish relationship between two or more variables (Orodho, 2009). Descriptive survey is a technique of collecting information through interviewing or administering questionnaires to a given sample of individuals (Orodho, 2009). This study sought to find out the relationship between self-efficacy and performance appraisal among public secondary school teachers' in Sabatia sub-county, Vihiga County, Kenya.

The study targeted five hundred and twenty (520) teachers employed by Teachers Service Commission (TSC) in public secondary schools in Sabatia Sub-county. These teachers are serving in the thirty-eight (38) public secondary schools including: one (1) national, four (4) extra county, five (5) county, and twenty-eight (28) sub-county. The sample comprised 237 teachers from 12 secondary schools. The teachers were sampled using stratified random sampling. Twelve (12) Principals and one (1) TSC Sub-County Director were sampled purposively. Instruments of data collection included questionnaires, interview guide and document analysis guide. Quality control of the research instruments was ensured through piloting, content validity and test retest for reliability. Quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS (version 25.0) descriptively and inferentially, while qualitative data was also analyzed thematically. The results from the data collected, are presented in frequency Tables, and percentages. The inferential statistics were tested using ANOVA test and t-test. The qualitative responses have been used in qualifying quantitative results, as well as different perspectives during discussions of the findings. Study Findings on Teacher's Self-Efficacy and Performance Appraisal

The study established self-efficacy amongst teachers by asking them to respond by ticking in the correct box which best describes them. The scores were put on a five-point Likert scale where; SA= Strongly Agree (5), A= Agree (4), N=Neutral (3), D= Disagree (D) and SD= Strongly Disagree (1). Summary of descriptive statistics was as presented in Table 1.

Results in Table 1 above show all mean values above 4. The study used a five-point Likert scale where 4 meant Agree. The standard deviations are all between 0 and 1

Table 1: Teacher's Self Efficacy

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself;	4.8015	.50414
When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them;	4.7265	.37956
In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me;	4.8950	.30729
I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind;	4.8858	.39577
I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges;	4.8721	.33469
I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks;	4.7808	.53105

Source: Field Data, 2021

implying a lower variance across the response from the participants of the study. The results therefore imply respondents are in agreement with all the statements regarding self-efficacy. These results agree with findings from interview schedules. A principal commented that all teachers in his school 'set goals to be achieved by the end

of each academic term and that the teachers' appraisal is based on the same.'

The study established descriptive statistics of performance appraisal. The respondents were asked to give their opinion showing the level of their agreement or disagreement with the statement provided on a Likert

scale of 1- 5 where: Strongly agree (SA)=5, Agree(A)= 4, Neutral (N)= 3, Disagree (D)= 2 and Strongly disagree (SD) =1. Table 2 presents the findings.

The statements recorded the scores as follows; I am punctual to work had a mean of 4.8356 with standard deviation of 0.44968. The statement mean was above the

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Performance appraisal

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
I am punctual to work	4.8356	.44968
I report to lessons in time	4.2100	.57604
I meet set deadlines	3.9817	.83481
I clear syllabus in time	3.8630	.85641
I improvise and use teaching and learning materials	3.9954	.88565
I integrate ICT in my lessons	4.2968	.52334
I have identified gaps after appraisal	3.6895	.84290
I have attended professional development courses	3.3014	.67085
Composite Mean and Standard Deviation	4.02168	0.70496

Source: Field Data, 2021

composite mean 4.02168, with a standard deviation less than 1, which is encouraged since it supports performance appraisal. From document analysis, records of teachers' lessons attendance and reporting register marked by learners confirmed that most teachers reported for lessons in time. I report to lessons on time had a mean of 4.21 with standard deviation of 0.57504 with a standard deviation less than 1. The statement mean was above the composite mean which is encouraged since it supports performance appraisal. When interviewed, a Principal had this to say about teachers' punctuality to work:

"As we speak now, the tool has really enhanced teacher performance in class. Besides that, I have never had problems with the issue of punctuality because teachers are aware of what they are supposed to do. Performance appraisal tool gives clear guidelines on what is to be done at what time." (Principal 6, 2021)

The statement 'I meet set datelines' had a mean of 3.9817 with standard deviation of 0.83481, a deviation less than 1. The statement was below the composite mean which needs enhancement to support performance appraisal. I clear syllabus on time had a mean of 3.863 with standard deviation of 0.85641, a deviation less than 1. The statement mean was below the composite mean and hence there is need to enhance clearance of syllabus to support performance appraisal process. According to Ekundayo, Konwea & Yusuf (2010), instances abound where teachers complain of lack of time to do certain things which they would have done. A good teacher must make effective use of his time to have time for everything he plans to do. Olaniyi (1998) pointed out that the most important asset a teacher should possess is the skill in managing his time. Such skill will enable the teacher to devote a balanced attention to interpersonal relations and production (Ekundayo *et al.* 2010). Barbara (2003) emphasizes that getting organized will help in being successful. Secrets of successful people range from controlling time, delegating, setting goals and priorities, overcoming paper overload to living within a budget. On time management tips, Barbara (2002) further stated that time management is about getting important things done and learning to do things more effectively.

The statement 'I improvise and use teaching and learning materials had a mean of 3.995 with standard deviation

of 0.88565 which was less than 1.'The statement 'I integrate ICT in my lessons' had a mean of 4.2968 with standard deviation of 0.52334. The statement mean was above the composite mean and therefore it encourages performance appraisal process. To underscore ICT integration a Principal said:

"We are able to integrate ICT in our teaching and learning process as a school. We have ICT tools like projectors, mobile phones, cameras for languages and computers. All this have made learning in schools better due to performance appraisal." (Principal 6, 2021)

Another principal said the following on the ICT gadgets use in learning and teaching;

"In my school, 80% of my teachers have integrated ICT in the process of learning and teaching. We have projectors, computers, laptops, mobile phones, document cameras for language teaching among others." The teachers who use ICT gadgets, are more confident in their work. They have a greater sense of initiative and are more motivated." (Principal I, 2021)

I have identified gaps after appraisal had a mean of 3.6895 with standard deviation of 0.8429. The statement mean was below the composite mean and therefore needs to be encouraged to enhance performance appraisal process. While I have attended professional development courses had a mean of 3.3014 with standard deviation of 0.67085. The statement mean was below the composite mean hence it does not support performance appraisal process. The main purpose of appraisal is to give the appraisee an opportunity to reflect on their work and learning needs in order to improve their performance (moghal, 2016). Teachers therefore need to be encouraged to identify gaps and come up with deliberate strategies to address them (gaps).

The TSC/TPAD/01 indicated that the purpose of ongoing appraisal was to review and improve teaching standards through a systematic appraisal approach with a view to evaluate teachers' performance and promote professional development so as to enhance learning outcomes. Its objectives are: to provide quality education to learners in all public institutions, to provide an opportunity for teachers to improve their performance competencies, to analyze performance gaps, to provide support for professional development, and to provide

a fair, effective and consistent teacher evaluation (TSC/TPAD/01). Professional development for teachers provides a wide range of interactive activities that are designed to improve the teacher's professional knowledge and skills, as well as their teaching practices and contribute to their growth. Teachers develop themselves professionally through training and retraining. Musset (2010) asserts that this is purposed to update, develop and broaden the knowledge that teachers had acquired during, and or provide them with new skills and professional understanding which improves the effectiveness of teachers. Training and retraining are seen as vehicles to improve teachers teaching effectiveness (Ngala and Odebero, 2010). Teachers getting involved in staff development programs particularly pursuing higher education and training motivate them into taking their teaching roles more seriously.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.617 ^a	.381	.304	3.26741

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-efficacy

Source: Field Data, 2021

appraisal. In other words, self-efficacy had a statistically significant influence on teacher appraisal. Further analysis of ANOVA was carried out to check whether the model was fit for the independent variable to explain the dependent variable. The findings were summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 showed the F-statistics was recorded as 310.745 at

Table 4: ANOVA Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	114.716	1	114.716	310.745	.001 ^b
	Residual	2316.690	217	10.676		
	Total	2431.406	218			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance appraisal

b. Predictors: (Constant), Self-efficacy

P-value was in parenthesis

Source: Field Data, 2021

Table 5: t-Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	22.499	3.264		6.894	.000
	Self-efficacy	.276	.084	.617	8.278	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Performance appraisal

Source: Field Data, 2021

CONCLUSION

1. Self-efficacy affects teachers' activity and productivity. Therefore, it must be enhanced in teachers.
2. Performance appraisal is significant in evaluating, quality control, planning and decision making among teachers in education institutions.
3. There was a statistically significant effect of teacher's self-efficacy on performance appraisal.

The study set out to test the following null hypothesis:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and teacher' performance appraisal among public secondary school teachers in Sabatia Sub-County, Vihiga County.

To test the hypothesis, the two variables namely self-efficacy and performance appraisal were put in a linear relationship and modelled through simple regression analysis;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$$

Where Y=Teacher Appraisal, X1= Self-efficacy, β_0 = y intercept and β_1 = Beta coefficient value for self-efficacy.

The model summary was presented in Table 3

the R value from the model summary of the regression between self-efficacy and performance appraisal was 0.617. The R square value was 0.381, which implied 38.1 % effect on self-efficacy was attributed to teacher

p=0.000, implying the model fit two variables. The t-test results of the two variables was summarized in Table.5.

The results show a constant t-value of 6.894 at p=0.000. When self-efficacy was introduced in the equation, the value increased to 8.278 at p=0.001. This implied self-efficacy had 1.384 unit change in teacher appraisal. The study rejected the null hypothesis.

RECOMMENDATION

1. There is need to enhance teachers' self-efficacy. Clear strategies and programs must be drawn and implemented to boost teachers' self-efficacy.
2. Performance appraisal needs to be enhanced more in schools since it plays a key role in service delivery. Through performance appraisal, teachers are able to prepare professional documents which enhance their confidence to teach thus boosting their self-efficacy.

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